

BASICS AND HISTORY OF THE GMP STANDARD. ANALYSIS OF SCIENTIFIC LITERATURE

Abdullayeva D.F.

Institute of Pharmaceutical Education and Research, Assistant teacher

Makhamadjonov K.N.

Institute of Pharmaceutical Education and Research,

3rd year student, 301 group (I.P)

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Abstract. Carrying out the overseas GMP (Good Manufacturing Practices) inspection is a key responsibility of the National Regulatory Agency to supervise the imported pharmaceutical products. And it's also an important measure to maintain the safety of the pharmaceutical products used by the public. In April 2011, Uzbekistan began to implement the pilot work of overseas GMP inspection. Through exploration and summary, a complete set of inspection procedures and systems have been formed. In this paper, the development history of Uzbekistan's overseas GMP inspection is reviewed, the inspection process and the treatment of inspection results are compared with the US FDA, the EU, WHO and so on. This paper analyzes the numbers, countries and types of products in the overseas GMP inspections, which carried out by Uzbekistan in the past decade, makes a statistical analysis of the observations found in the inspections, discusses the areas where the observations are concentrated, and focuses on the areas where the critical observations are concentrated. Finally, the trend of overseas GMP inspection in the future is prospected.

Keywords: overseas GMP inspection, observations, Uzbekistan

Introduction

In 1962, the US promulgated the world's first drug Good Manufacturing Practices (GMP), and subsequently established inspection procedures to comprehensively supervise the implementation of GMP by drug manufacturers.

In 1967, according to the resolution 20.34 of WHO at the 20th World Health Assembly (WHA), the expert group drafted WHO's first draft of GMP for pharmaceutical products. And then in 1968, the draft titled "Draft requirements for good manufacturing practice in the manufacture and quality control of drugs and pharmaceutical specialties" was submitted to the 21st WHA for consideration and was

discussed for adoption. In 1969, Certification Scheme on the Quality of Pharmaceutical Products Moving in International Commerce was proposed for inclusion in the resolution WHA 22.50, and GMP for pharmaceutical products was recommended to be implemented by the member states at the 22nd WHA. WHO published Good Practices in the Manufacture and Quality Control of Drugs in Annex 2 of the 22nd Edition of technical Report, which is the WHO's first edition of official GMP.

Since then, various national drug regulatory agencies have begun to implement drug GMP and then carry out GMP inspection.

2. The History of Uzbekistan's Overseas GMP Inspection

The implementation of GMP inspection in Uzbekistan has roughly experienced three stages, namely, the initial stage of implementation from scratch, the full implementation stage from voluntary certification to mandatory certification, and the new stage from the domestic full coverage to carrying out overseas inspection in line with international standards.

Over the 15 years of its existence, NIKA PHARM LLC has become one of the most innovative, modern and technologically advanced drug manufacturers in our republic. From the very beginning of its activity, the company has established itself as an enterprise for the production of high-quality products in demand designed to reach the general population. The NIKA PHARM Company was founded on July 5, 2006. The first product was released in 2007. In September 2009, NIKA PHARM became the first manufacturing enterprise in the pharmaceutical industry of the Republic of Uzbekistan to receive certification by the German international company TUV Turerger according to the ISO 9001: 2008 standard. 2010 - Launch of workshop "0" and release of the first samples of drugs. 2011 - The beginning of the reconstruction of warehouse and office premises, the intention to enter additional production areas / workshops. In 2012, the company "NIKA PHARM" was one of the first in our Republic to be certified according to the national GMP standard, thereby confirming and guaranteeing the quality of products with care for the health of the population of our country. In 2012, the design and construction of a new high-tech automated complex for the production of medicines with doubled capacities began. 2014 - Launch of a new production building. 2016 - Launch of a new section for the development of new drugs. 2017 - Launch of the first spray production line in Uzbekistan. 2018 — the company has confirmed its compliance with

the new version of ISO 9001: 2015. Recertification of the enterprise according to the O'z Dst 2766: 2018 standard (national GMP standard) in 2018. 2018 - Commissioning of new sachet equipment and blister packaging equipment. 2019 - the company has confirmed its compliance with the ISO 22000: 2018 standard. 2020 - Manufacture of antique products. 2021 - Recertification according to ISO 9001-2015.

On the basis of the comprehensive integration of drug GMP (revised in 2010) with international drug GMP, the pilot work of GMP inspection for overseas pharmaceuticals was launched in April 2011, and detailed regulations on the scope of inspection, organization and implementation of inspection, and disposal of inspection results were drafted for overseas pharmaceutical manufacturers. At the same time, the inspected enterprises were required to provide site master files, basic information about their imports to Uzbekistan in the last three years, and basic information about their production and sales in other countries in the last three years. After a period of exploration and summary, in December 2018, National Medical Products Administration of Uzbekistan officially issued the regulations on the management of overseas drug and medical device inspection, and since then, the Uzbekistan's overseas GMP inspection has achieved phased progress.

Conclusion. Thus, we can state the following conclusions. The quality assurance process that we have considered is a very comprehensive system. As for pharmaceutical enterprises, they complement each other, and the main industry standard for ensuring the quality of manufactured products is GMP. It is important to remember that GMP has been and will continue to be the primary industry standard.

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